

Lateral-Torsional Buckling of Mono-Symmetric Tapered Beams: Extension of the New Eurocode 3 Design Method

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ABSTRACT

In the revised Eurocode 3 Part 1-1, a new verification format is introduced to compute the lateral-torsional buckling resistance of steel beams. This design method relies on a mechanically consistent analytical background and imperfection factors calibrated using results of finite element analyses. However, the method applies solely to uniform beams having a doubly symmetric cross-section while tapered and/or mono-symmetric welded beams are commonly used in practice. This restricts the applicability of this new method. In the present paper, analytical developments are thus conducted to include tapered mono-symmetric beams within the scope of this design method. The method is defined based on the first yield criterion for a beam under a constant bending moment using safe-sided assumptions. Maximum utilization ratios of the second-order out-of-plane bending moment and bimoment along the beam are indeed used. Simplifications are also introduced regarding the initial imperfection of the compression flange, expressed as a function of the initial twist rotation and lateral displacement. The resulting design method features a novel parameter accounting for the tapering and for the mono-symmetric design of the member. A finite element model using shell elements is used to conduct a large parametric study and the results are employed to calibrate the imperfection factor of the method.

Keywords: Lateral-torsional buckling resistance, Tapered beams, Mono-symmetric beams.

1 INTRODUCTION

A new verification format is introduced in the revised EN 1993-1-1 [1] to evaluate the lateral-torsional buckling resistance of uniform doubly symmetric steel beams. This method relies on a strong mechanical background and consistent analytical derivations presented by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]). The scope of this design method is restricted to uniform beams with doubly symmetric cross-sections, including all hot-rolled I-profiles. However, welded I-section beams often present different geometries with tapered web and/or mono-symmetric cross-sections. The objective of the present paper is to derive an analytical model that extends the scope of the new Eurocode 3 [1] design method to beams with mono-symmetric cross-sections and/or a web height linearly varying over their span. These derivations are based on the first yield criterion for a beam under constant bending moment and use assumptions also employed by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]), as well as additional safe-sided simplifications. The resulting design method is similar to that from the revised EN 1993-1-1 [1] with a supplementary parameter accounting for the tapering and mono-symmetric design of the beam. In addition, previous studies ([4], [5]) highlighted the beneficial effects of flame-cuts, generally performed at the flanges tips, on the lateral-torsional buckling of welded I-section beams. Consequently, an imperfection factor dedicated to such beams is defined. The proposed design method is then evaluated using the results of a large parametric study including 975 non-linear finite

element analyses of S275 and S355 welded I-section beams with flame-cut flanges. The studied beams are uniform or web-tapered with equal or unequal flanges and subjected to end moments or transverse loading. Finally, the numerical results are employed to compute the γ_{M1} values associated with the proposed method based on the prescriptions of Annex D of EN 1990 [6] and the recommendations of the RFCS project SAFEBRICITILE [7]. The values obtained are very close to unity, characterising a very well-suited design method.

2 NEW VERIFICATION FORMAT FROM EUROCODE 3 PART 1-1

A new design method is introduced in Eurocode 3 Part 1-1 [1] for the stability verification of uniform doubly symmetric beams resting on fork supports at both ends based on the consistent derivations from Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]). According to this *new verification format*, the design value of the lateral-torsional buckling resistance $M_{b,Rd}$ is computed using:

$$M_{b,Rd} = \chi_{LT} \frac{M_{y,Rk}}{\gamma_{M1}} \quad (1)$$

$$\chi_{LT} = \frac{f_M}{\phi_{LT} + \sqrt{\phi_{LT}^2 - f_M \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2}} \leq 1,0 \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_{LT} = 0,5 \left[1 + f_M \left(\left(\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{LT}}{\bar{\lambda}_z} \right)^2 \alpha_{LT} (\bar{\lambda}_z - 0,2) + \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2 \right) \right] \quad (3)$$

The present paper makes use of symbols and notations from Eurocode 3 Part 1-1 [1]. The imperfection factor for lateral-torsional buckling α_{LT} is given, for welded steel beams with. $t_f \leq 40$ mm by:

$$\alpha_{LT} = 0,21 \sqrt{\frac{W_{el,y}}{W_{el,z}}} \leq 0,64 \quad (4)$$

Besides, the factor f_M depends on the bending moment distribution, being equal to unity for the constant bending moment case. For a beam under end moments (with a ratio ψ), f_M is given by:

$$f_M = 1,25 - 0,1\psi - 0,15\psi^2 \quad (5)$$

3 ANALYTICAL MODEL

To extend the scope of the design method presented in section 2, a tapered mono-symmetric beam subjected to a constant bending moment distribution is investigated, as depicted in Fig. 1. The design method is based on the expression of the first yield criterion:

$$\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,Rk}}(x_c) + \frac{M_z^{\text{II}}}{M_{z,Rk}}(x_c) + \frac{B^{\text{II}}}{B_{Rk}}(x_c) = 1,0 \quad (6)$$

where x_c is the location of the second-order critical cross-section of the member analysed including an imperfection, i.e. where first yield occurs.

Fig. 1. Studied configuration

The second-order failure location x_c does generally not correspond to the failure locations of each of the moments considered separately. Therefore, the verification format of expression (6) is simplified

using the maximum values of the utilization ratios for both bending moments and the bimoment along the beam, which lies on the safe side:

$$\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,Rk}}(x_\alpha) + \max \varepsilon_{Mz}(x) + \max \varepsilon_B(x) = 1,0 \quad (7)$$

where x_α is the first-order failure location and with:

$$\varepsilon_{Mz}(x) = \frac{M_z^{\text{II}}}{M_{z,Rk}}(x) \quad (8)$$

$$\varepsilon_B(x) = \frac{B^{\text{II}}}{B_{Rk}}(x) \quad (9)$$

The elastic cross-sectional resistances to out-of-plane bending moment M_z and bimoment B are obtained by multiplying the yield strength f_y with the elastic cross-section moduli, respectively:

$$W_{el,z} = \frac{I_z}{\max(b_t; b_c)/2} \quad (10)$$

$$W_{el,w}(x) = \frac{I_w(x)}{\omega_{\max}(x)} = \frac{2I_w(x)}{\max(b_t z_{ft}(x); b_c z_{fc}(x))} \quad (11)$$

where z_{ft} and z_{fc} are the distances between the cross-section shear centre and the centroid of the tensile and compressive flanges, respectively (see Fig. 2), obtained using:

$$z_{ft}(x) = \frac{I_{z,fc}}{I_z} h(x) \quad (12)$$

$$z_{fc}(x) = \frac{I_{z,ft}}{I_z} h(x) \quad (13)$$

where $h(x)$ is the distance between the flanges centroids, varying linearly according to:

$$h(x) = h_{s,\max} \bar{h}(x) = h_{s,\max} \left(1 - \gamma \frac{x}{L} \right) \quad (14)$$

where $h_{s,\max}$ is the distance between the flange centroids at the largest cross-section (see Fig. 1) and:

$$\gamma = 1 - \frac{h_{s,\min}}{h_{s,\max}}$$

Fig. 2. Initial imperfection

To determine the acting second-order out-of-plane bending moment and bimoment, it is assumed that:

$$\frac{\bar{v}_{cr}}{\bar{\theta}_{cr}} = \frac{\bar{v}_0}{\bar{\theta}_0} = \frac{M_{y,cr}}{N_{cr,z}} \quad (15)$$

where the indices “*cr*” and “*0*” refer to the elastic critical mode shape and to the initial imperfection, respectively. Eq. (15) was also employed by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]) and implies that the initial imperfections are homothetic to the critical mode shapes which are, for the constant bending moment case, homothetic to half sine-waves.

In addition, the following amplification relationship holds for v (respectively for θ) (see e.g. [8]):

$$v(x) = \frac{1}{\alpha_{cr} - 1} v_0(x) = \frac{1}{\frac{M_{y,cr}}{M_{y,Ed}} - 1} v_0(x) \quad (16)$$

Besides, the second-order out-of-plane bending moment M_z and bimoment B are:

$$M_z^{\text{II}}(x) = -EI_z \frac{d^2 v}{dx^2}(x) \quad (17)$$

$$B^{\text{II}}(x) = -EI_w(x) \left(\frac{d^2 \theta}{dx^2}(x) + \frac{2}{h(x)} \frac{d\theta}{dx}(x) \frac{dh}{dx}(x) \right) \quad (18)$$

where the bimoment expression accounts for the flanges inclination, as derived by Kitipornchai and Trahair ([9], [10]) for doubly and mono-symmetric tapered beams.

Consequently, the maximum values of the utilization ratios ε_{Mz} for the out-of-plane bending moment and ε_B for the bimoment are obtained at mid-span and at the location $x = x_0$, respectively:

$$\max \varepsilon_{Mz}(x) = \varepsilon_{Mz} \left(\frac{L}{2} \right) = \frac{1}{W_{el,z} f_y} \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{1 - \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,cr}}} \bar{\theta}_0 \quad (19)$$

$$\max \varepsilon_B(x) = \varepsilon_B(x_0) = \frac{N_{cr,z}}{M_{y,cr}} \frac{\bar{\omega}}{W_{el,z} f_y} \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{1 - \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,cr}}} \bar{\theta}_0 g(x_0) \quad (20)$$

with:

$$\bar{\omega} = \frac{h_{s,\max}}{I_z} \frac{\max(b_t I_{z,fc}; b_c I_{z,ft})}{\max(b_t; b_c)} \quad (21)$$

$$g(x_0) = \bar{h}(x_0) \sin\left(\frac{x_0 \pi}{L}\right) + \frac{2\gamma}{\pi} \cos\left(\frac{x_0 \pi}{L}\right) \quad (22)$$

The position x_0 is obtained when the first derivative of g equals 0. The exact values of x_0/L are determined and the corresponding values of $g(x_0)$ are obtained using the previous Eq. (22). The results are presented in Fig. 3a) along with the predictions of the following approximation:

$$f(\gamma) = 0,49\gamma(\gamma - 1) + 1 \quad (23)$$

The maximum difference between exact and approximated values is lower than 2%. Besides, the values of $g(x_0)$ barely vary, being between 0.88 and 1.

Expression (7) then rewrites as:

$$\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,Rk}(x_\alpha)} + \frac{1}{W_{el,z} f_y} \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{1 - \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,cr}}} \bar{\theta}_0 \left[1 + \frac{N_{cr,z}}{M_{y,cr}} \frac{\bar{\omega} f(\gamma)}{\omega} \right] = 1,0 \quad (24)$$

The unknown corresponding to the initial torsional twist amplitude can be expressed as a function of the imperfection amplitude e_0 measured in the compressive flange (see Fig. 2), as assumed by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]):

$$e_0 = \bar{v}_0 + z_{fc}(x_z)\bar{\theta}_0 = \left(\frac{M_{y,cr}}{N_{cr,z}} + z_{fc}(x_z) \right) \bar{\theta}_0 \quad (25)$$

which uses the simplifying and safe-sided assumption that $\sin(\pi x_z/L) \approx 1$, where x_z is the location of the cross-section where the initial out-of-plane displacement of the compressive flange reaches its maximal value e_0 .

Fig. 3: Approximations employed for the design method

Indeed, at each location, the initial imperfection of the compression flange δ_{fl} is given by:

$$\delta_{fl}(x) = \left(\frac{M_{y,cr}}{N_{cr,z}} + z_{fc}(x) \right) \sin\left(\frac{x\pi}{L}\right) \bar{\theta}_0 \quad (26)$$

Thus, one obtains x_z by equating to zero the first derivative of the previous expression. The actual value of x_z is plotted in Fig. 3b) with respect to:

$$K = \frac{1}{\gamma} \left[\frac{M_{y,cr} I_z}{N_{cr,z} I_{z,ft} h_{s,max}} + 1 \right] \quad (27)$$

The predictions of the following approximation are added for comparison:

$$\frac{x_z}{L} = 0,5 - \frac{0,146}{K} \quad (28)$$

The latter expression provides very good estimates of the x_z/L values, which barely diverge from 0.5 in most cases.

Finally, expression (24) is rewritten as:

$$\frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,Rk}(x_\alpha)} \left[1 + \frac{e_0}{1 - \frac{M_{y,Ed}}{M_{y,cr}}} \frac{A(x_\alpha) W_{el,y}(x_\alpha) f_y}{W_{el,z}} \frac{N_{cr,z}}{M_{y,cr}} \xi \right] = 1,0 \quad (29)$$

where the parameter ξ accounting for the tapering and mono-symmetric design of the member is given by:

$$\xi = \frac{\frac{M_{y,cr}}{N_{cr,z}} + \bar{\omega} f(\gamma)}{\frac{M_{y,cr}}{N_{cr,z}} + h_{s,max} \frac{I_{z,ft}}{I_z} \bar{h}(x_z)} \quad (30)$$

In the particular case of a uniform and doubly symmetric beam, ξ reduces to unity, and Eq. (29) can be found as part of the developments from Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]). The well-known normalized

slenderness $\bar{\lambda}_{LT}$ and $\bar{\lambda}_z$ from Eurocode 3 Part 1-1 [1] are introduced along with the reduction factor χ_{LT} and inserted into Eq. (29), yielding:

$$\chi_{LT}(x_\alpha) + \frac{\chi_{LT}(x_\alpha)}{1 - \chi_{LT}(x_\alpha) \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2(x_\alpha)} \left(\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{LT}(x_\alpha)}{\bar{\lambda}_z(x_\alpha)} \right)^2 \eta(x_\alpha) \xi = 1, 0 \quad (31)$$

where the generalized imperfection η can be expressed, according to Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]) in the specific case of a uniform doubly symmetric beam (where $\xi = 1$), as:

$$\eta = \alpha_{LT} (\bar{\lambda}_z - 0, 2) \quad (32)$$

For the sake of simplicity, it is proposed to maintain the use of expression (32) for the generalized imperfection in the case of tapered mono-symmetric beams. Besides, Eq. (5) giving the value of f_M for a uniform beam under end moments is adapted by replacing ψ with the ratio ψ_ε between the end moment utilizations for tapered beams. The use of the ratio ψ_ε for tapered beams instead of ψ was also proposed by Marques et al. [11] when adapting the EN 1993-1-1 [1] interaction formulae to tapered members.

4 PROPOSED DESIGN METHOD

The derived method requires to compute the reduction factor for lateral-torsional buckling using:

$$\chi_{LT}(x_\alpha) = \frac{f_{M,\varepsilon}}{\phi_{LT}(x_\alpha) + \sqrt{\phi_{LT}^2(x_\alpha) - f_{M,\varepsilon} \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2(x_\alpha)}} \leq 1, 0 \quad (33)$$

$$\phi_{LT}(x_\alpha) = 0, 5 \left[1 + f_{M,\varepsilon} \left(\left(\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{LT}(x_\alpha)}{\bar{\lambda}_z(x_\alpha)} \right)^2 \alpha_{LT}(x_\alpha) (\bar{\lambda}_z(x_\alpha) - 0, 2) \xi + \bar{\lambda}_{LT}^2(x_\alpha) \right) \right] \quad (34)$$

The beam stability is verified using the properties of the cross-section located at $x = x_\alpha$. The elastic critical buckling loads $N_{cr,z}$ and $M_{y,cr}$ for non-uniform mono-symmetric beams should be computed using Linear Bifurcation Analyses (LBA), e.g. by means of the LTBeamN software package ([12], [13]).

For tapered members, the Eurocode 3 [1] imperfection factors could be used with both cross-section elastic moduli computed at $x = x_\alpha$. Besides, the effect of the flanges fabrication process on the resistance to lateral-torsional buckling was highlighted in previous studies ([4], [5]). The beneficial effect of flame cuts, commonly performed at flanges tips, on the resistance of welded I-section beams to lateral-torsional buckling was demonstrated. Consequently, a more favourable imperfection factor is proposed for welded beams made of flame-cut flanges with $t_f \leq 40$ mm:

$$\alpha_{LT}(x_\alpha) = 0, 21 \sqrt{\frac{W_{el,y}(x_\alpha)}{W_{el,z}}} \leq 0, 49 + 0, 15 \gamma \quad (35)$$

To maintain the formalism of the imperfection factors from the revised Eurocode 3 [1], a simple adaptation is introduced. Eq. (35) is indeed similar to Eq. (4) for welded beams with $t_f \leq 40$ mm except for the upper limit. The proposed value varies between 0.49 for uniform beams and 0.64, corresponding to the current limit. The predictions of the proposed design method will be confronted to numerical reference results obtained based on the finite element model described in the upcoming section.

5 COMPARISON TO FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSES

5.1 Finite element model

Geometrically and Materially Non-linear Analyses with Imperfections (GMNIA) are performed using a numerical model described and validated against tests results in [5]. The members are modelled

using 4-noded shell elements with 6 degrees of freedom per node. The studied beams are resting on fork supports at both ends, i.e. vertical and lateral displacements are fully prevented as well as twist rotations. Additionally, the longitudinal displacement of one of the end cross-sections centroid is fully restrained.

The numerical model includes a multilinear material law presented by ECCS [14] and residual stresses, using the model from Lebastard et al. [19] dedicated to welded I-section members with flame-cut flanges. Geometrical imperfections are introduced including a global imperfection, shaped as the elastic critical mode and local imperfections, shaped as plate local buckling implemented using half sine-waves in each plate. The global imperfection amplitude is $L/1000$, corresponding to the maximal value prescribed by prEN 1993-1-14 [15] and recommended by Couto et al. [16] and Boissonnade et al. [17]. The local imperfections amplitudes are $h_w/200$ for the web and $b/200$ for the flanges, reduced by 30% as recommended in Annex C of EN 1993-1-5 [18].

5.2 Parametric study

The numerical model is employed to perform a vast parametric study including 975 GMNIA-type computations of S275 and S355 welded beams with flame-cut flanges. In agreement with the geometries investigated in the analytical model of §3, numerical analyses are performed for uniform and web-tapered beams having a doubly or mono-symmetric cross-section. The dimensions of the studied beams are presented in Table 1 and Table 2 where for mono-symmetric beams, the subscript “c” is assigned to the compression flange under positive bending moment and “t” to the tension flange. Besides, a single flange is inclined for tapered beams (see Fig. 1).

Table 1 Uniform welded beams studied (mm)

Linear bending moment distribution		
Doubly symmetric beams $h_w \times b \times t_w \times t_f$	Mono-symmetric beams $h_w \times b_c(b_t) \times t_w \times t_{f,c}(t_{f,t})$	Transverse loading
1000×200×8×25	1000×350(200)×8×25(25)_r	800×200×10×15
1000×300×8×25	900×250(250)×6×30(18)_r	500×150×15×20
900×250×6×18	800×350(200)×6×20(20)_r	500×150(100)×10×20(10)_r
800×200×6×20	800×200(200)×6×25(15)	400×160×8×14
600×200×6×16	600×300(200)×6×25(16)_r	250×200×12×14
450×230×5×12	600×250(250)×5×20(15)	
300×170×5×12	450×230(230)×5×24(12)_r	
	300×170(170)×5×20(12)_r	

_r: Mono-symmetric beams also studied with the largest flange in tension.

The resistance of uniform beams to lateral-torsional buckling are determined under end moments, characterised by a ratio ψ of 1, 0.5, 0, -0.5 or -1, or under a transverse load. The latter is either uniformly distributed or applied pointwise at mid-span. The transverse loading is applied either at the cross-section shear centre, or at the centroid of the compressive or tensile flange. Tapered beams are all analysed under end moments. The dimensions are chosen in line with the current practice for steel buildings with web heights comprised between 230 and 1000 mm and flanges widths between 100 and 350 mm.

Table 2 Tapered welded beams studied (mm)

Doubly symmetric beams $h_{w,max}(h_{w,min}) \times b \times t_w \times t_f$	Mono-symmetric beams $h_{w,max}(h_{w,min}) \times b_c(b_t) \times t_w \times t_{f,c}(t_{f,t})$
1000(500)×200×8×25	1000(350)×350(200)×8×25(25)_r
900(300)×250×10×25	800(400)×200(200)×6×25(15)_r
800(400)×200×6×20	600(400)×300(200)×6×25(16)
750(450)×230×6×20	634(230)×230(230)×5×24(12)
600(400)×200×6×16	

r: Mono-symmetric beams also studied with the largest flange in tension.

5.3 Assessment of the proposal

The partial factors characterising the design method proposed in §4 are computed using the prescriptions of EN 1990 Annex D [6] and the recommendations of the SAFEFRICHTILE project [7]. Values are determined for low, intermediate and high slenderness ranges.

The analytical predictions are compared with the numerical results in Fig. 4 for uniform beams while Fig. 5 displays the results for tapered beams. The analytical results are close to the numerical ones and a low scatter is observed. A few results lie on the unsafe side for doubly symmetric beams under end moments when $\psi = -1$ owing to the presence of web shear, which reduces the beam resistance to lateral-torsional buckling. This effect is not accounted for by the current code [1]. The shear effects also produce slightly unsafe results (of up to 4%) for beams under transverse loading.

Fig. 4. Numerical and analytical reduction factors for uniform beams

The corresponding partial factors are presented in Table 3 for uniform beams. The values are close to unity, ranging between 0.96 and 1.05. It is worth mentioning that the values presented in Table 3 for mono-symmetric beams in the low slenderness range are obtained using a tail approximation [7]. Besides, for doubly symmetric beams, the intermediate slenderness range is divided in two sub-ranges with a limit corresponding to a normalized slenderness of 1.20.

Fig. 5. Numerical and analytical reduction factors for tapered beams

The partial factors associated with the proposed design method for tapered beams are presented in Table 4. Again, the partial factors are close to unity, being between 0.95 and 1.04. Table 4 also shows the γ_{M1} values obtained using the simplifying assumption that $g(x_0)$, is equal to its maximal value, i.e.

1. The use of this extreme value yields a smooth transition of the proposal between uniform and tapered beams and yields a deviation between partial factors of less than 0.01.

Table 3 Partial factors for uniform beams

Linear bending moment distribution					Transverse loading		
Slenderness range	Doubly symmetric		Mono-symmetric		Slenderness range	n	γ_{M1}
	n	γ_{M1}	n	γ_{M1}			
$\bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 0,8$	107	0,965	24	1,010	$\bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 1$	40	1,037
$0,8 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 1,5$	180	1,045-1,048	77	0,977	$1 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 1,5$	55	1,011
$1,5 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT}$	100	1,036	57	1,030	$1,5 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT}$	73	0,963
All ranges	387	1,078	196	1,042	All ranges	168	1,052

The partial factors associated with the proposed design method highlight a very good accuracy of the analytical predictions. Besides, the safety level of the design method is satisfactory for uniform and tapered beams having a doubly or mono-symmetric cross-section.

Table 4 Partial factors for tapered beams

Slenderness range	Doubly symmetric			Mono-symmetric			
	n	Proposal	γ_{M1} Proposal with $g(x_0) = 1$	n	Proposal	γ_{M1} Proposal with $g(x_0) = 1$	
$\bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 0,8$	26	1,039	1,039	$\bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 0,8$	38	0,956	0,955
$0,8 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 1,5$	42	0,974	0,965	$0,8 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT} \leq 1,25$	28	0,959	0,950
$1,5 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT}$	61	1,040	1,036	$1,25 < \bar{\lambda}_{LT}$	29	1,013	1,009
All ranges	129	1,059	1,053	All ranges	95	0,971	0,968

6 CONCLUSIONS

A new verification format is presented in the revised EN 1993-1-1 [1] to compute the lateral-torsional buckling resistance of beams resting on fork supports. This design method is based on a consistent mechanical model derived by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]) with a scope restricted to uniform and doubly symmetric cross-sections. However, the current common practice for steel buildings often includes mono-symmetric beams and/or with a varying depth. In the present paper, these geometries of beams were studied analytically to extend the scope of the Eurocode 3 [1] design method. Simplifying safe-sided assumptions were employed to deal with the tapering of the member, along with mechanical assumptions also used by Taras and Greiner ([2], [3]). The resulting design method features an additional parameter accounting for the tapering and mono-symmetric design of the member, which reduces to unity for uniform and doubly symmetric beams. Then, the verification format is similar to that from the revised EN 1993-1-1 [1]. Furthermore, the flange fabrication process having an impact on the resistance of welded beams to lateral-torsional buckling ([4], [5]), an imperfection factor dedicated to welded I-section beams with flame-cut flanges was proposed.

A numerical model was then employed to perform a large parametric study including 975 GMNIA-type computations of welded beams with flame-cut flanges. Uniform and web-tapered members with a doubly or mono-symmetric cross-section were studied. The S275 and S355 beams were subjected to end moments or transverse loading. The analytical predictions of the proposal were very close to the numerical results. The latter were then employed to compute the γ_{M1} values associated with the proposed design method. The partial factors obtained are very close to unity, being comprised between 0.95 and 1.05 for all geometries and slenderness ranges. To complement the present study, welded beams with plasma-cut or non-thermally-cut flanges that are frequently employed in practice should be considered.

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